

D1.5 Policy feedback to the EOSC Partnership

Project Title	Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions
Project Acronym	RDA TIGER
Grant Agreement No	101094406
Instrument	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Topic	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-04
Start Date of Project	1 January 2023
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Work Package	WP1 - Management
Lead Author (Org)	Ari Asmi (RDA-A)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Secreteriat), Ryan O'Connor (RDA-A)
Due Date	31.12.2023
Date	30.12.2023
Version	1.1 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10444664

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
1.0	1.12.2023	Ari Asmi	Internal circulated version
1.1	29.12.2023	Ari Asmi, Hilary Hanahoe, Ryan O'Connor	Submitted version, with response from the RDA secretariat

Disclaimer

RDA TIGER has received funding from the European Commission’s HORIZON Coordination and Support programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101094406. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

RDA	Research Data Alliance
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
EOOSC	European Open Science Cloud
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions

Executive Summary

This deliverable answers to the Commission request for a policy feedback regarding the RDA TIGER in the wider EOSC and policy environment. It specifies the potential policy impact of the RDA TIGER supported Working Groups, and describes wider policy recommendations from the project and RDA in general.

EOSC POLICY BRIEF

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01

TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-04

PROJECT: RDA TIGER

PROJECT WEB SITE: [RDA TIGER website](#)

GRANT NUMBER: 101094406

DATE: 2023-12-31

SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief enables EU-funded projects contributing to the advancement of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to report on progress and provide input for further policy analysis and development by the European Commission. This policy brief should be understood as complementary to the other mandatory reporting materials.

Policy background:

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices across the [European Research Area](#) (ERA). As such it contributes to several actions of the [ERA policy agenda](#) (in particular ERA action 1 & 8). EOSC is also recognised in the [European strategy for data](#) as the data space for science, research and innovation which shall be fully articulated with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy.

Overall progress is steered by the EOSC tripartite governance involving the Union represented by the European Commission, the participating countries represented in the EOSC Steering Board and the research community represented by the EOSC Association. The second phase of development of EOSC (2021-2030) takes place in the context of the EOSC European co-programmed Partnership, which brings together the European Commission and the EOSC Association.

The [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA) co-developed with the entire EOSC community sets 3 General Objectives (GO), 14 Operational Objectives (OO) and 14 Action Areas (AA).

General Objectives (GO):

1. Open science becomes the 'new normal', by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.
2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.
3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

Operational Objectives (OO):

1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;
2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023);
3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership;
4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership;

5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing);
6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership;
7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025;
8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership.
9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership.
10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024;
11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025;
12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025;
13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users;
14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023.

<u>Action Areas (AA) of a technical nature:</u>	<u>Action Areas (AA) related to boundary conditions:</u>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifiers 2. Metadata and ontologies 3. FAIR metrics and certification 4. Authentication / authorisation infrastructure 5. User environments 6. Resource provider environments 7. EOSC Interoperability Framework 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Rules of Participation 9. Landscape monitoring 10. Business models 11. Skills and training 12. Rewards and recognition 13. Communication 14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global

More information can be found from:

- https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-science-cloud>
- <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about>

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS (MAX 6P)

- A. Overview of contributions in relation to the EOSC policy and EOSC SRIA objectives. Please briefly describe the main contributions of the project so far in relation to the General Objectives (GO) of the EOSC SRIA. As far as possible, please indicate the relation between each contribution and the most relevant Operational Objective(s) (OO) and Action Area(s) (AA) of the EOSC SRIA.

Example: AA3 - OO7 - OO13: Project contribution ... Link to deliverable (if applicable)
(Further information and context can be found in sections 5, 6 and 8 of the [SRIA](#))

The RDA TIGER is a **support project**, aiming towards supporting the creation and activities of Research Data Alliance Working Groups. These Working Groups in turn support the EOSC policy and SRIA activities development in the global environment, as well as the overall development of Open Science and Open Science policies, practices and technologies in Europe and globally. This process is intended to support the wider landscape development around the EOSC and SRIA objectives, creating the necessary environment in Europe and internationally to ensure the success of the EOSC.

Currently, the RDA TIGER supports 14 RDA Working Groups (or potential groups preparing to become an official WGs), with 2 groups already finishing their activities and two more being started. The list below indicates the overall impact of the RDA TIGER project in general to the EOSC and EOSC SRIA objectives, as well as the potential or realised WG outputs which have policy relevance in the fields indicated.

Overall project outputs with potential policy importance

AA14: RDA TIGER provides mechanism for internationalisation service of the EOSC derived outputs (e.g. in INFRA-EOSC projects) via the supported WGs, and the relevant dissemination via the project and RDA channels. This is described in the project website, and is marketed directly to the relevant projects and research infrastructures.

AA9-AA14: RDA TIGER landscape database is being finalised in 2023, with first version of the RDA outputs and WGs (among others), many relevant to the EOSC projects and EOSC policy goals. This graph database is the basis of further landscape analysis in the project and will also include more EOSC-project outputs in 2024.

Supported WG work with potential policy importance

RDA TIGER supports and facilitates the process, but does not directly contribute as an author. It should be noted that *creation of these Working Groups is already a significant output*, as they form a platform for the INFRA EOSC projects to impact, interact and interoperate with the global community.

GO3-OO6-AA14-OO9: Supported group *Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy technical repository service providers WG* provides a platform to develop repository certification for domain specific repositories, which has a strong potential impact to act as a key mechanism for EOSC communities to identify qualities of such repositories, as a part of the EOSC ecosystem. Engagement in this group is strong from many EOSC-involved repositories in Europe, but has a significant international partnership.

GO2-AA2- AA14-OO3: Several Working Groups supported by RDA TIGER:

- *WG Multilingual Vocabularies Alignment* is a new starting WG working on aligning multilingual vocabularies in the SSH fields internationally, based on the European developments, lead by the key ESFRI infrastructures in the SSH field.

- *WG Small uncrewed aircraft systems data* is a new starting WG working on harmonising the environmental sector data from automated systems (not limited to aircrafts, including e.g. marine drones). This WG will in output create domain-specific recommendations for these data types.
- *Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG* is a new group supporting FAIR data terminology and metadata development in materials science field. *Recommendations for FAIR data sharing in wind energy WG* is a new starting WG working on international harmonisation of energy field data. This has also impact on the relevant ESFRI infrastructures and commercial wind energy providers.
- Starting group on *Immune system digital twins WG*, will provide international harmonisation of Digital Twins data and processes in the medical sector.

GO2-AA14-OO4: *FAIRification of the Genomic Annotations WG*, is a starting WG on globally harmonizing genomic data annotations, originally created in many EOSC related projects within the biomedical European ESFRI infrastructure cluster.

GO2-GO3-AA5-AA6-AA7-AA14-OO1-OO2-OO10: *Global Open Research Commons WG* output created a model to identify the different services of internationally relevant large Open Research Commons with commonly agreed terminology and ontology. The group has also mapped some of the key “EOSC-analogues” around the world, and this harmonized data is a key initial source of information on the progress outside of the European region in this field.

GO1-GO3-AA14-OO1: *National PID strategies WG* provided a key list of recommendations for Member state (and other countries) strategies for implementing PIDs in their infrastructures.

GO2-AA14-OO7: The group *PRO4RS - Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software* is key new WG working together with Research Software Alliance creating a wide range of recommendations on research software management and organization for Research Performing Organizations. This has a high potential to impact institutional research policies, and thus also for their use of EOSC services. The group activities should be closely monitored and (preferably) participated by relevant EOSC-projects and other EOSC developers.

B. Key contributions subject to wider dissemination by the European Commission. Describe in more details the key contributions of your project *which you judge ready for wider dissemination* amongst the EOSC community. Typical examples include inspiring EOSC use cases, guidelines, toolkits, services, policies and good practices supporting any of the 3 EOSC Strategic Objectives. For each reported use case, please indicate to which of the following categories it best relates to:

- Assessment (eg incentives/rewards for researchers to practise open science¹)
- Data (eg research data management and research data that are open and/or follow the FAIR principles)
- Engagement (eg research that engages and involves citizens via citizen science)
- Infrastructure (eg data repositories, data stewardship, preservation of research outputs)
- Publications (eg research publications that are available in open access, licencing of publications, retention of IPR for publications)
- Services (ie services that enable research output discovery and exploitation, e.g. services for the execution of research workloads and code or for the visualisation, analysis, and sharing of research data)
- Skills/training (skills and training for researchers to practise open science)
- Software (eg open source software)

The current RDA TIGER groups are mostly upcoming in their outputs; however, RDA TIGER has supported two more advanced groups in activities. These are not directly created by the RDA TIGER project, but the project has supported their creation and dissemination.

¹ See also <https://coara.eu/>

The Global Open Research Commons International Model (available in [here](#), with links to specific spreadsheets)

In response to the global movement to implement national and cross-national or global commons, a Research Data Alliance (RDA) Interest Group was formed to work towards a community-developed typology for describing research commons. This Interest Group created a Working Group to develop an International Model describing the attributes of Global Open Research Commons. This document supports the release of this RDA Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model (IM) v. 1.0, presented as a spreadsheet. This accompanying narrative document provides background information about the initiative, describes its intent and intended audience, the method used to create it, its structure and content. It also provides brief descriptions of communities and activities that have proposed to, or are currently, utilising the model in different contexts, as well as next steps for work in this area. It is important to recognise that the model is aspirational in nature and not prescriptive, drawing on existing good practice and promoting inclusive approaches. It is important to recognise that the model is aspirational in nature and not prescriptive, drawing on existing good practice and promoting inclusive approaches.

Policy relevance: This model provides a basis of a global research commons typology and necessary components. This is crucial to created international interoperability of large research commons, as the individual components need to be properly identified and categorised for effective comparison and joint development. Notably this model is also suitable for smaller Commons, and is currently investigated for Member state commons mapping and comparison, also in the Research Performing Organisation level.

National PID strategies (available [here](#))

The RDA National PID Strategies WG has produced a comparison guide and checklist that can be used when developing a national PID strategy. This is supported by the nine case studies collected from countries at different stages of developing a national PID strategy. The countries are Australia, Canada, Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, the Netherlands, New Zealand, South Korea, and the United Kingdom.

The guide offers a comparison of the nine case studies, including scope, drivers, strategy development, key features and priority PIDs. The checklist can be used as a starting point for developing your national PID strategy. You do not need to complete all of the numbered points or follow the order. The checklist is designed to be used flexibly to help you think about what is needed.

Policy relevance: This PID strategy checklist could be more widely used in the European Member state level to facilitate creation of PID strategies and overall development of the national level infrastructures and contributions to the EOSC. This document is only the first step on such development though, and further investments from the national level is needed. However this RDA group membership could provide a long-term peer support platform for such developments in Europe.

C. Synergies with other stakeholders. If policy relevant, please describe the interactions and synergies of your project with other EOSC stakeholders (e.g. the EOSC-Association, other EU-funded projects, national authorities, research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures or others), with related international initiatives or with the communities involved in the development of the other data spaces of [the European data strategy?](#)

The RDA TIGER is deeply synergetic with most of the EOSC environment, as it is designed to provide the necessary support activities for international alignment and joint development. The connection to the EOSC Association is close, and the RDA TIGER community and the EOSC-A have had a series of close collaborative

actions, particularly in the development and progress of the EOSC-A driven Horizon Europe Technology and Communication groups. The main targets of this activity have been with EOSC projects and research infrastructures, which are considered as prime targets for RDA TIGER working groups, however due to development stage of the projects involved, this has not yet created as many connections as originally envisaged. Further developments in this field is expected from the EOSC “Winterschool” in January 2024, where all of the INFRA EOSC projects are present in a technical level workshops, with potential to create new WGs based on those activities. A key finding has been this far that many of the INFRA EOSC projects have reserved fairly small effort for such external alignment, making creation of effective working groups more challenging.

- RDA TIGER has also directly been involved with several EU funded projects, with particular interest on *EOSC FUTURE*, where the Ambassador programme led to creation of several Working Groups and long-term activities in fields of science not previously connected to either RDA or the EOSC. Collaboration in development of interoperability has also been built together with *WorldFAIR* outputs (particularly FARI implementation profiles), with potential new WGs to be found shortly. Similar connection exists with *FAIR IMPACT*.
- RDA TIGER is also connected to the international initiatives outside of Europe, either directly as RDA community members (several US open science related projects, Australian ARDC activities), Working Group members, or via other international communities, such as CODATA or UN bodies. These connections are mostly handled via collaboration with the global RDA secretariat, but could be further leveraged in the next steps of the RDA TIGER activities. Notably, the RDA US has started a pilot programme to provide similar facilitation services as RDA TIGER, clearly highlighting the international need for these services.
- RDA TIGER is also involved in several Digital Twins initiatives in Europe, with intention to create a common platform within the RDA for DT common issues and challenges.
- RDA TIGER has also started discussion with the Data Spaces Support Centre for supporting key WGs for their internationalisation interests and takes a part in the DSSC online workshops. Similar discussions have also been initiated with the CoARA secretariat for data-related evaluation-of-science developments.

D. EOSC challenges and lessons learnt of a policy nature. Please briefly describe the main challenges that your project encountered regarding technical development, cooperation, support, dissemination and/or exploitation of the project’s deliverables into the EOSC context. Do you have policy recommendations to help addressing these challenges?

The RDA TIGER project itself has the following key observations based on the first year of operations:

- Getting existing INFRA EOSC projects to join or start RDA groups is proved to be more challenging than anticipated. This is somewhat understandable, as a starting project needs to concentrate on their own developments but does not take into account that the most cost-effective way to do internationally significant developments is to engage with the communities directly from the initial development phase. As the projects are not required explicitly to do international engagement, such activities are seen as extra work and not necessarily done, even with the support provided by the RDA TIGER. *Policy recommendation: For any project which would potentially benefit from engagement in the international level, this could be included in the project calls and grant agreement as a task which requires resource allocation.*
- Similarly, using RDA to highlight and present the existing project outputs from EOSC and ESFRI infrastructure-related projects would be very useful for creation of common standards globally, and to ensure the highest impact of the resource commitments to these initiatives. RDA can provide long term community to ensure the usage of the project outputs, and dive way to their global acceptance as community de facto standards. This pathway is not yet used for its fullest potential, partly due to resource issues (mentioned above), but partly due lack of knowledge. RDA TIGER uses some resources to advertise these tools, but dissemination from the Commission side could be also seen as a beneficial, particularly when considering the project output sustainability during project reviews. *Policy recommendation: Commission could consider RDA (and other similar community platforms) as a way to create sustainability for project outputs. These should be more directly disseminated to relevant projects (also outside of EOSC, e.g. on Data Spaces or infrastructure initiatives), even in the starting phase of the project when first drafting the plans for output sustainability.*

- Organisational and timing issues with other international bodies make the international collaboration sometimes challenging. Collaboration and discussion between key funding organisations in different regions could make of RDA-driven EOSC supporting activities more impactful. Similarly, involving RDA in key international collaborative actions (e.g. in research infrastructures or global research collaboration actions) could be beneficial for these activities, as RDA could bring the necessary transparent, equal, and community-driven framework for long-term collaboration. *Policy recommendation: Direct collaboration with global funding environment on Open Science and research data in particular. This could involve more efficient timing of support or funding opportunities, and aligning policies in the global research environment. Involving RDA explicitly or implicitly in the Commission actions towards key research collaboration areas (e.g. Latin America, Africa, South-Eastern Europe, ASEAN countries, etc.).*
- Some of the support mechanisms are difficult to provide for researchers or contacts from countries not involved in the Horizon Europe programme. These have been mostly overcome with the help from the REA, and the overall rules are well established by now, but there are still issues which require high level authorisation (e.g. organising meetings outside of Europe, which are quite central for RDA). *Policy recommendation: Future grants on international collaboration could include specific clauses which reduce the necessary special permissions for limited support to 3rd countries not involved in the Horizon Europe programme.*

In addition to these project-based policy recommendations, we have also included more general RDA recommendations for Open Science in general:

Research Data Alliance Recommendations on Open Science from a global perspective, addressing funders and policy makers across the world:

1. The paradigm for Open Science must change if it is to be inclusive and ensure everyone can participate in it. Ultimately, we should leave no one behind. We run the risk of developed countries having the resources to push their Open Science vision and practices while less developed countries will be beneficiaries and not active participants. Therefore, investment in infrastructure, resources and skills for Open Science are imperative. *Specific EOSC context: ensure EOSC is globally communicated, easily accessible by scientists and researchers across the globe.*
2. Prioritisation of data standards and application of new technologies to harmonise research data so it can be more easily shared and used. This continues to be a huge barrier to achieving Open Science and accelerating data driven innovation. The development of data standards and technical infrastructure will improve data quality and trust in data. Furthermore, it enables researchers to concentrate on undertaking research without having to become experts in ‘Open Science’ and research data management practices. *Specific EOSC context: ensure standards and best practices are encouraged and integrated in EOSC.*
3. Invest in team science. Investment in data support staff, such as, data stewards, data managers research software engineers, community managers, data scientists, and recognise their role and contribution to the Open Science agenda. As technology advances, research performing organisations need multidisciplinary teams to support research projects and deal with the increasing complexity of data. *Specific EOSC context: ensure EOSC funded projects have dedicated effort to support data science activities.*
4. Inclusion of the scientific community in the definition of the Open Access and Open Science visions, agendas and policies by decision makers and policy makers. The scientific community has direct, first-hand experience, and a clear understanding of the challenges and barriers to be addressed. *Specific EOSC context: ensure community driven consultation and dialogue on future phases of EOSC development and service delivery.*
5. Reward, recognise and support the diversity of roles and responsibilities, and their importance in the overall academic research ecosystem. *Specific EOSC context: encourage and reward recognition in EOSC related activities.*
6. Proactive Consortia funding of infrastructure with an understanding that developed countries and scientific communities should subsidise some of the cost for less developed countries and communities. *Specific EOSC context: ensure that connections with less developed countries are encouraged and support by EOSC.*

7. Funders should align their policies and investments to reduce financial waste and duplication of efforts.
Specific EOSC context: ensure and facilitate dialogue and information exchange between global research data and open science funders.

E. Link to other EU policy priorities (beyond EOSC). Is your project contributing to advance other policy priorities of the EU (e.g. [Horizon Europe Missions](#), Sustainable Development Goals, EU sectoral policies or others)? In case of positive reply, please list those EU policy priorities and explain briefly the nature of the project's contributions.

Commission priority **Stronger Europe in the World** is the most central of the priorities for the RDA TIGER. The project directly brings the developments provided by EOSC and several other open science initiatives to the global environment, and supports creation of global standards and processes based on the European developments. This is further supported by the number of participants in the RDA groups from the priority areas of Africa and Western Balkans. Several of the supported working groups support the work towards **EU missions** indirectly, e.g. via harmonising the data formats and documentation.